

A Comprehensive SOC-OCV Hybrid Model for Turnigy Graphene 5000 mAh Lithium-Ion Batteries Using Gradient Iterative Algorithm

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Abstract— In Lithium-Ion Batteries (LIBs), the relationship model between State of Charge (SOC) and Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) must be adaptive, simple, robust, and accurate especially in real-time SOC estimation. Besides, the model must be able to characterize LIB in large-scale temperatures to ensure its validity at any ambient conditions. Thus, this paper presents a hybrid model developed to express the relation between SOC and OCV. The improved model has proven its efficiency when applied to Turnigy Graphene 5000 mAh LIB. The model combines logarithmic, linear, and exponential functions with six parameters. The gradient-based iterative search method which is considered one of the best algorithms is used to optimize and adapt the model parameters. The RMSE of the developed hybrid model (13 mV) is always less than the RMSE of the old polynomial model except at -10 °C. Finally, the developed hybrid model demonstrated great efficiency at most temperatures and was superior to the old polynomial model.

Keywords—Lithium-ion batteries; OCV model; SOC estimation; model-based methods; polynomial model; hybrid model; battery management system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are broadly used in many electronic applications especially in electric vehicles owing to their various brilliant characteristics, including large voltage window, high energy storage, small self-discharge rate, extended cycle life, and low contamination [1–4]. To keep batteries in their safe operating area and achieve safety and reliability, a battery management system (BMS) is highly required to manage and protect LIBs [5–7]. One of the vital roles of BMS is to properly estimate the state of charge (SOC) of the batteries [8,9]. SOC is an essential parameter that indicates the residual capacity in the battery [10]. The charging/discharging operations are depending on the estimated value of SOC [11]. Moreover, battery performance stands out by the accurate SOC. Precise SOC estimation may not only preserve the battery, avoid over-discharge, and increase battery cycle life, but also let the application enhance rational control approaches to save energy. Therefore, a precise SOC estimation guarantees efficient management for the battery. The accurate SOC estimation has many obstacles because of the non-linearity behavior of the batteries, inexact primary SOC, and heavy computation in real-time applications [12]. Numerous SOC estimating approaches have been presented in the literature. As illustrated in Fig. 1, these approaches are divided into three main categories: direct measurement [13,14], data-driven approaches [15,16], and model-based methods [17,18].

The direct methods are open loop methods that depend on the direct measurements from the battery like current, voltage, and impedance. These methods are characterized by their simplicity and easy implementation. However, noise during measurements can cause accumulative errors and there is no error correction [14].

Data-Driven methods are characterized by their high accuracy in SOC estimation [19]. These methods have the feature of error self-correction, they can learn to adjust the battery parameters by reducing the error between the simulated voltages and the measured voltages to produce an accurate SOC. On the other hand, complex hardware is required which results in increased implementation cost. Moreover, an extensive amount of test data such as voltage, current, temperature, and historical values is necessary for accurate estimation. Heavy data processing and long computation are considered a hindrance for applying this procedure in economic BMSs [15].

Model-based methods are considered highly accurate methods to estimate the SOC. They are based on the deep analysis and understanding of the battery. Battery modeling has a vital role in assessing its performance and predicting its dynamic response under various conditions (Temperature, charging/discharging current, and voltage). The complete process of model-based SOC estimation may be divided into two steps [20]: (i) battery modeling and (ii) algorithm implementation. These algorithms can surpass the disadvantages of direct measurement methods because they exhibit improved adaptability and robustness due to the closed-loop feedback procedure [21]. Even though, the accuracy estimation and algorithm robustness are greatly dependent on the accuracy of the model. Kalman filter (KF) is the most popular and effective technique in model-based methods. It is used for linear devices however, Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) is used for non-linear devices like LIBs [22].

Two issues are related to general model-based methods, which result in low estimation accuracy. First, the EKF typically linearizes nonlinearities in battery models, resulting in a significant truncation error in SOC estimation results. Second, when the Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) is imprecise, it causes a large fault in SOC estimation. OCV is the voltage at the battery terminal when there is no load, and the battery is in a steady state. From this point, an exact OCV model to describe the relationship between SOC and OCV is essential in model-based methods to achieve highly accurate SOC estimation [21]. Therefore, some researchers have presented various methods to describe the relationship between SOC and OCV, each with distinct advantages and disadvantages. In [23], an OCV model based on exponential and hyperbolic fittings was proposed to describe the faradic reactions of lithium-iron phosphate batteries. It showed a high accuracy but it is not adaptable for different types of LIBs. Moreover, a high-accuracy OCV model based on the LIB diffusion standard was proposed in [24]. Nonetheless, it revealed complexity in parameters identification which limits its usage in real-time applications. In addition, a dynamic hysteresis model was employed in [25], it was applied on multiple LIBs, But also, it is not suitable for real-time applications.

Inspired by the previous studies, this article focuses on expanding the main ideas reported in [26]. Applying a hybrid OCV model to rebuild the relation between SOC and OCV with many distinguishing features that are considered particularly significant for model adjusting in online applications. Where, the model employs four major functions to describe the basis electrochemical reactions covering little, mid, and large SOC ranges. Besides, the model fits the data sets from the experimental tests over a wide temperature range with great accuracy. Furthermore, the model is straightforward and has fewer parameters than was used in common current models. The hybrid OCV model shows a higher accuracy than a polynomial model for the same LIB at various temperatures. Besides, the model is outstandingly appropriate for real-time parameter updating because of its simplicity. Parameters of the proposed hybrid model were optimized using a nonlinear iterative algorithm at five different classes of temperature to check the model temperature sensitivity. In Section 2, the relationship between SOC and OCV will be presented. In addition, Section 3 illustrates the comprehensive hybrid model in detail. Moreover, Section 4 demonstrates the Gradient Iterative algorithm to identify the model parameters. Finally, result and discussion will be exposed in Section 5 to study the hybrid model and show its validity at wide range of temperatures to ensure its efficiency and applicability.

Fig. 1 Classification of SOC estimation methods.

II. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOC AND OCV FOR LIBS

To describe the relationship between SOC and OCV and build a lookup table, a system consisting of a battery, current/voltage sensors, and electrical cards is used to carry out the intermittent charge test. In this test, the battery is charged with C/10 of its capacity till it attains full capacity (100%). OCV is measured after each 10% of the battery SOC during charging. The battery should stay in open circuit mode for 1h to reach a steady state and accomplish equilibrium voltage to measure accurate and precise OCV [19]. The algorithm of battery charging and computing OCV is presented in Fig.2. In this research, a data set of Turnigy Graphene 5000 mAh Li-ion Battery [27] and the lookup table of (SOC, OCV, and T) was used. The choice of Turnigy battery was not random but for many important reasons. Turnigy Graphene packages use carbon in the battery construction to build a thin layer of graphene that is only 0.335 nm thick, which makes it the thinnest battery electrode recognized to mankind, when compared to traditional LIB technologies, the graphene atoms form a quite dense compound that facilitates electrons movement with small resistance. As a result, the battery can maintain higher power density while remaining cool under load connection [28]. Because temperature and resistance are normal problems of batteries, graphene nature has safely miniaturized these issues, resulting in an incredible increase in cycle life. These features qualify this type of lithium battery for use in applications with high energy and power needs such as electric cars which made the choice fall on this type to work on. Table 1. illustrates the characteristics of Turnigy Graphene LIB. Moreover, the SOC versus OCV was outlined in Table 2. and plotted in Fig.3 at (T = 25°C).

Table 1. Characteristics of Turnigy Graphene LIB.

Model	Graphene 65 C
Rated capacity	5000 mAh
Specific power	7.3 KW/kg
Specific energy	134 Wh/kg
Normalized resistance	14 mΩAh
Rated voltages	3.55 to 4.2 V

A hybrid model was investigated to fit SOC-OCV mapping data properly, and then compared with the traditional polynomial model that is usually used to describe the SOC-OCV relationship [29]. The polynomial model was presented in Eq. (1). Where $p_n, p_{n-1}, p_1,$ and p_0 are the polynomial model parameters. However, the hybrid model divided the curve into sectors according to the electrochemical function. The illustrated model includes exponential, linear, and logarithmic functions to fully fit the SOC-OCV curve. In the next subsection, the Hybrid OCV comprehensive model will be discussed in detail.

$$OCV(SOC) = p_n soc^n + p_{n-1} soc^{n-1} + \dots + p_1 soc^1 + p_0 soc^0 \tag{1}$$

Fig. 2 OCV measurement procedure.

Table 2. OCV versus SOC of Turnigy Graphene LIB.

OCV	SOC
3.53	10 %
3.68	15 %
3.69	20 %
3.73	30 %
3.77	40 %
3.81	50 %
3.85	60 %
3.91	70 %
4.0	80 %
4.1	90 %
4.15	95 %
4.19	100 %

Fig. 3 OCV versus SOC at 25 °C.

III. HYBRID SOC-OCV MODEL FOR LITHIUM-ION BATTERY

The electrochemical examination of several LIB types confirms that a three-section SOC-OCV model has a higher potential for capturing all of the distinctive aspects of the electrochemical processes that have been reported [26]. Eq. (2) illustrates the suggested comprehensive hybrid SOC-OCV model, and it is easy to discern a logarithmic function with real (not complex) power, a linear function, and an exponential function with a shifted exponent.

$$V_{OCV} = a + b \cdot (-\ln soc)^m + c \cdot soc + d \cdot e^{n(soc-1)} \quad (2)$$

Where $m > 0$, $n > 0$, V_{OCV} and soc stand for the battery's OCV and SOC respectively. If charge accumulations on the active material surfaces occur within the LIB, the logarithmic function needs to be adjusted to take center stage at low SOC. The intermediate SOC range, where the fundamental battery redox reactions take place (reduction and oxidation), is dominated by the linear function. The high SOC behavior, which includes both charge accumulation and partial redox reaction, is subsequently influenced by the final exponential function. Consequently, the three functions in Eq. (2) are crucial, and they will cooperate to create the hybrid OCV model throughout the complete SOC range. Accordingly, Eq. (2) presents the SOC-OCV model of just four proportionately scaled terms, whose factors are a , b , c , d , m , and n . The SOC-OCV mapping that is needed can be achieved by real-time tweaking of just these four factors. As a result, there is a significant reduction in the difficulty of realizing Eq. (2), which is beneficial for real-time state estimation. In the next section, the model's parameters optimization will be described in detail.

IV. SOC-OCV MODEL PARAMETERS IDENTIFICATION

For a certain type of LIB, Eq. (2) has six parameters that should be precisely identified from the offline experimental data or recorded data set. This is a nonlinear identification owing to the logarithmic and exponential parts in the comprehensive hybrid equation. Thus, a typical non-linear optimization algorithm is required, and it is typically executed iteratively. The gradient-based iterative search technique is one of the best algorithms to optimize the model parameters [30,31]. It is based on the following mathematical formula, which is stated in terms of the unidentified parameter vector $\Theta = (a, b, c, d, m, n)$.

Substitute in Eq. (3) a lookup table consists of a relation between soc and V_{OCV} in N steps of $(soc(k), y(k))$, where $k=1, 2, \dots, N$. Eventually result in the following equations:

$$V_{OCV} = a + b \cdot (-\ln soc)^m + c \cdot soc + d \cdot e^{n(soc-1)} \quad (0\% \leq soc \leq 100\%), m > 0, n > 0 \quad (3)$$

$$y = F(soc, \Theta) = V_{OCV} = a + b \cdot (-\ln soc)^m + c \cdot soc + d \cdot e^{n(soc-1)} \quad (4)$$

$$y(k) = F(soc(k), \Theta) + e(k), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (5)$$

$$Y = F(soc, \Theta) + E \quad (6)$$

Where:

$$Y = [y(1), \dots, y(N)]^T, soc = [soc(1), \dots, soc(N)]^T, E = [e(1), \dots, e(N)]^T$$

Thus, an estimation problem involving nonlinear least squares has been formed. Finding the parameter vector that can diminish the subsequent expression is the goal,

$$\min_{\Theta} \mathcal{E}(\Theta) = \frac{1}{2} (Y - F(soc, \Theta))^T (Y - F(soc, \Theta)) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Let } G(\Theta) = \left(\frac{\partial F(soc, \Theta)}{\partial \Theta} \right)^T$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & (-\ln s_1)^m & s_1 & e^{n(s_1-1)} & b \cdot [\ln(-\ln s_1)] \cdot (-\ln s_1)^m & d \cdot (s_1-1) \cdot e^{n(s_1-1)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & (-\ln s_N)^m & s_N & e^{n(s_N-1)} & b \cdot [\ln(-\ln s_N)] \cdot (-\ln s_N)^m & d \cdot (s_N-1) \cdot e^{n(s_N-1)} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (8)$$

Typically, the procedure needs to be carried out repeatedly, utilizing the gradient-based procedure given as follows:

$$\Theta_{j+1} = \Theta_j + \mu_j G(\Theta_j)(Y - (F(soc, \Theta))) \quad (9)$$

Where the selection of the step value μ_j is necessary to guarantee method convergence. The algorithm terminated once the $\|\Theta_{j+1} - \Theta_j\|$ is less than the pre-established minimal threshold.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we study the validation of the proposed model and exposed its improved fitting with the experimental data which made it distinct and superior to the traditional polynomial model. Moreover, examination of the hybrid model applicability at different temperature to verify its robustness at different conditions.

A. Validation of Comprehensive OCV Model

To verify the generalized hybrid OCV model for Turnigy Graphene Li-ion Battery, a data set of SOC-OCV lookup table from the experimental tests is compared with the estimated hybrid OCV model and polynomial OCV model at room temperature ($T = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). As shown in Fig. 4, the hybrid model (red line) is more congruent with the experimental data (blue line) than the polynomial model (green line), especially in the middle region of SOC when the redox reactions of the battery exist regularly (SOC from 15% to 80%). This result approves the benefits of the hybrid model for the Turnigy battery because the SOC middle region is the most usable region in electrical applications especially electric vehicles. Subsequently, the hybrid model will have a positive impact on real-time SOC estimation. The parameters of the OCV hybrid model is 3.52, -0.020, -0.556, 1.24, 2.91, and 1.53, respectively. Applying Eq. (10) to calculate the RMSE between the comprehensive hybrid OCV model and traditional polynomial OCV model with the experimental data sets [32].

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N 2(\text{OCV Model (i)} - \text{OCV experimental (i)})^2} \quad (10)$$

The RMSE between the hybrid OCV model and the experimental OCV data is 13 mV which is less than the RMSE of the conventional polynomial OCV model (17 mV) by 4 mV at $T = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The error between the estimated hybrid OCV model and experimental OCV values occurs at the edges of SOC which is not considered a critical issue because the middle SOC is the most usable region as stated before.

Fig. 4 Comparison between polynomial function and hybrid function to extract the relation between OCV and SOC at room temperature ($T = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

B. Temperature Variation Sensitivity Analysis of the Proposed OCV Model

The estimated OCV hybrid model, OCV polynomial model, and experimental data for the Turnigy Graphene Li-ion Battery are illustrated in Fig. 5 at various temperatures ($T = -10, 0, 10, 25,$ and $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Fig. 5 Comparison between hybrid OCV model and polynomial OCV model at various temperatures (a) -10, (b) 0, (c) 10, (d) 25, and (e) 40 °C. The parameters of the estimated OCV hybrid model at different temperatures are presented in Table 3. The subsequently RMSE of the old polynomial model and the new hybrid model are also introduced in Table 4. at different temperatures.

Table 3. Parameters Identifications of OCV Hybrid Model for Turnigy Graphene Li-ion Battery at Different Temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>n</i>
-10 °C	3.77	- 0.087	- 0.528	0.96	1.37	2.01
0 °C	3.39	- 0.006	-0.754	1.57	4.43	1.37
10 °C	3.52	- 0.015	-0.657	1.34	3.38	1.53
25 °C	3.52	-0.020	-0.556	1.24	2.91	1.53
40 °C	3.54	-0.026	-0.491	1.15	2.56	1.56

Table 4. Comparison Between RMSE of the OCV Hybrid Model and OCV Polynomial Model.

Temperature (°C)	RMSE of hybrid OCV model (mv)	RMSE of polynomial OCV model (mv)
-10 °C	13.6	12
0 °C	13	24
10 °C	13	19
25 °C	13	17
40 °C	13	17

The hybrid OCV model proved its robustness and efficiency when applied at different temperatures. The RMSE of the hybrid model is always less than that of the polynomial model except at -10 °C, but this is not considered a major problem because this very low temperature is not common for batteries to be used at.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The relation between SOC and OCV is divided into three regions (logarithmic, linear, and exponential) according to the electrochemical behavior of LIBs (charge accumulation, redox reactions, or both together). A hybrid model was investigated to describe these three regions. The model has six parameters which are identified using a gradient-based iterative algorithm. The new model was compared with the old polynomial model and highlights its robustness, simplicity, and accuracy. It has RMSE of ~13 mV at -10 °C, 0 °C, 10 °C, 25 °C, and 40 °C. on the other side, the old polynomial model has RMSE of 12, 24, 19, 17, and 17 mV at -10 °C, 0 °C, 10 °C, 25 °C, and 40 °C respectively. Thus, the new hybrid model is more accurate than the old model. These results lead to a great impact on SOC estimation in online applications like electric vehicles.

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